

CHARACTERISTICS OF CULTURE AND CIVILIZATION AND LAWS OF DEVELOPMENT

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ANNOTATION

This article examines the specific features of culture and civilization and the laws of development. The article also makes scientific and philosophical conclusions that culture and civilization are understood as concepts that at first glance mean the same thing, but have different meanings and laws of development. In the article, in the process of studying specific aspects of culture and civilization, the following points are of great importance. If culture is a phenomenon associated with education and the assimilation of social requirements, then civilization is a process associated with the emergence of the state, a sense of citizenship among members of society, and the formation of a sense of respect for state laws.

Keywords: *culture, spirituality, civilization, culture, Medina, urbanity, value, knowledge, education, ethics, knowledge, religion, faith, people, society, state.*

Introduction. At first glance, the concepts of culture and civilization seem like terms that mean the material development and spiritual image of society. But if we think based on the content and essence of these concepts, we will realize

that each of them is a set of separate concepts that have their own characteristics and relative independence from each other. When it comes to culture, when we analyze the concept of culture from a philosophical point of view, we understand it as a whole social phenomenon. Culture is the process of human activity, the material and spiritual values created as a result of it, and is a social phenomenon that is an important factor in human development.[1] When studying the historical, scientific-theoretical and practical aspects of the concept of culture, first of all, it is necessary to pay special attention to the etymology of the origin of this concept.

Main part

Today, most of the definitions given to the concept of culture in scientific literature are close to each other in content. In some sources, "culture" is derived from the Latin word "culture", which means education, including "primary cultivation of the land", and in some sources, "culture" - Arabic "medina" means urban"[2], - written as. Culture is a term formed by adding the suffix "iyat" to the Arabic word "Madina", and in Uzbek this word means "belonging to the city" concepts specific to the development of science and enlightenment in their content and essence point to the fact that people have progressed in the urban way of life. We can see that many peoples of the world explain the concept of culture with the term "Kultura" adopted from the Greek language. In our opinion, culture is a product of human conscious activity, mental potential, inner experience, worldly concepts.

Culture is not only a sum of material and spiritual wealth created by the creative activity of people, but also a criterion of the development of society. That is, the sum of knowledge, standards and values in society is embodied in culture. In the study of culture, it is possible not to use traditional ideas about objective laws, causality of events. Culture is always closely connected with man and cannot live without him. But as a complex, integrated unit of reality, it is

independent in its laws of development and existence. It is richer and deeper than the spiritual life of concrete social groups that embody cultural heritage. Culture will always be the largest store of values, a treasure of experiences. Generations of mankind use it and contribute to it.

A person interacts with culture in the following areas:

- firstly, culture adopts it as an object of influence;
- secondly, it operates in a concrete cultural environment as a carrier and representative of cultural values;
- thirdly, it develops culture as a subject of cultural creativity.

During social development, our ancestors passed the path from primitive life to high cultural development. Simple work tools have become the most advanced technological work tools today, dwellings made of wood and stone have become modern houses today. All this is being realized as a result of the tireless work of mankind over the centuries.

Central Asian encyclopedist Abu Nasr Farabi was the first to create a consistent doctrine about the origin, goals and tasks of society in the conditions of the Middle Ages. This doctrine covers many issues of a civilized society - state management, education, morals, enlightenment, religious beliefs, war and peace, labor and others. Culture is not only a collection of material and spiritual values, but also a creative activity. Also, Farabi says in his work "The City of Virtuous People": The outlook of virtuous people has an altruistic, humanistic nature. Their idea of happiness depends on the idea of goodness. Because a person cannot be happy without goodness[3].

So, according to Farabi, the city of virtuous people is the concept of an ideal state in which the idea of goodness is celebrated. The idea of goodness is connected with the concept of "primary existence" in Farabi's views and is deified. According to Farabi, a city of virtuous people can emerge only when a part of mankind reaches the level of divine consciousness. And the individualistic

and egoistic imaginations of the majority lead them to ignorance, and their cities remain ignorant. It can be seen that Farabi is a supporter of socialization, a supporter of living with the pain of the people, a supporter of goodness.

It is worth noting that although the material and spiritual types of culture were recognized in the research conducted in the field of civilization and culture in the former USSR within the framework of Marxist ideology, it was mainly approached from the point of view of historical materialism, that is, any civilization and the development of culture, the cultural development of society as a whole, was first of all connected with economy and materiality. For this reason, in this period, not enough attention was paid to the field of spirituality and its analysis. In this field, except for some scientific works, deep scientific and philosophical researches were not carried out. Rather, it was not possible to conduct scientific work. As a result of this, only the materialistic approach was decided in the research of the fields of civilization and culture, as in all fields.

In the process of researching the specific aspects of culture and civilization, we should pay serious attention to the following. If culture is related to education and mastering of social requirements, civilization is related to the emergence of a state, the formation of a sense of citizenship among members of society, and the formation of a sense of respect for state laws.

Results and Discussions. It is very important to distinguish the important elements of culture and civilization in determining the specific aspects of culture and civilization. The following can be cited as important elements of culture:

- Knowledge, understanding, imagination, views and scientific theories.
- Objectification and realization of this knowledge, imagination, views, theories.
- In this process, the formation and improvement of the human personality.

Each of the elements of culture is interrelated, and in the process of the formation of the human personality, the humanistic and progressive essence of

culture is manifested. In the existing scientific literature, there are cases of distinguishing between material and spiritual culture and even contrasting them. Some researchers associate civilization with material culture (technique, technology). In our opinion, it is rather controversial and unprospective to associate civilization with only one aspect of culture. Because in the scientific literature of cultural studies, culture is considered as a whole social historical phenomenon.

The most important features of early civilization include:

- Emergence of the state, emergence of writing.
- Separation of agriculture from crafts.
- Division of society into classes.
- Emergence of cities.

The following can be cited as important signs of modern civilization:

- Existence of the rule of law.
- Seeking to resolve conflicts between states, peoples, and social classes on the basis of common consensus.
- The development of social division of labor worldwide.
- Availability of communication system.
- Formation of planetary consciousness, planetary morality.

In the process of researching the processes of culture and civilization, the scientific heritage left by the scientists of European and Asian countries is of great importance. One such scientist was Oswald Spengler from Germany. The first volume of Spengler's selected works was published under the title "The Decline (Death) of the Western World", which predicted the consequences of civilizational progress. He presented history as a kaleidoscope of eight "organic" cultural and historical types: Egyptian, Indian, Babylonian, Chinese, Greco-Roman, Magical (Byzantine-Arab), Western European, and Maya. The ninth is the culture of the future, known as Russian-Siberian[4]. According to Spengler,

cultures appear “like flowers in the field” with impeccable purpose and leave nothing on the scene as if they had left the scene without a purpose. Spengler described the emergence of culture very beautifully and delicately, but culture does not leave the “scene” aimlessly, but loses its place and importance significantly due to the entry of another new culture. As a result, another civilization will be founded.

The morphology of Spengler's culture informed the Western world of its uncontrolled decline: according to Spengler, rationalistic civilization represents the destruction of the highest moral values of a culture doomed to death. According to Spengler, the great culture of the past seems to have shown the West its destiny, its immediate historical future. Of course, these ideas have been confirmed to this day. Why? A spiritually mature, intelligent society will always be able to create new things, to create the ground for the start of new civilizations in its place. According to Spengler, the comparative analysis of cultures reveals the unity of their fate. Every culture goes through the same sequence of developmental phases, and the main characteristics of each period remain the same in all cultures. All cultures are similar in terms of life expectancy (about 1000 years) and development rates. Historical events related to one culture left their traces in all other cultures. Every culture exhausts its internal creative possibilities, dies and passes to the stage of civilization. At this point, we would say that the end, the highest peak of the development of every culture is the foundation of a new civilization.

O. Spengler writes in the introduction to “Sunset of Europe”: “There is no absolutely right or wrong point of view for the true connoisseur of people”. Spengler also put forward ideas such as: “There are no eternal truths”, “There is no universal morality, there are as many cultures as there are morals”. Of course, there is no “universal morality”, it is impossible. Because each person is a separate living organism, a single worldview and a single thought. “As many

cultures as there are morals” - cultures have survived in different forms from different eras to us, and there are some changes in their practice and approach. But as culture increases, moral standards increase proportionally.

From the second half of the 19th century, the concepts of “civilization” and “culture” began to be differentiated. In the beginning, civilization meant high economic, cultural and spiritual development, and to a large extent religious development (for example, according to Spengler, religion is the basis of every civilization), later spiritual development was more associated with culture. started The essence of culture is now associated with forms and levels of spirituality that represent a high civilization and its great achievements[5].

One of the laws of development of culture is inheritance. That is, the law of passing past experiences to generations on the basis of inheritance. Succession means continuity, continuity, gradualness. This is a vertical development from the bottom up, from a simple expression of culture (imagination, imagination) to a complex view (mysticism, theoretical views). The concrete form of succession is expressed in inheritance. Production, science, technology, examples of monumental art, political, moral, artistic values - developed on the basis of inheritance. Another important law of cultural development is gradualism, that is, evolutionary, gradual development. Each form of culture, form of expression, is polished from generation to generation over the centuries, perfected and developed slowly, step by step, embodying positive values (ancient ethics, art, philosophy, mysticism, culture of the 21st century and b.). Each generation contributes to it, raises it to a new level and passes it on to the next generation. This is an evolutionary process[6].

Mythological thought played a major role in the formation of ancient Eastern culture. This culture is based on tradition. The tradition and experience of the ancestors were evaluated as absolute truth. D.S. Likhachev stated that decency was connected with the rule of absolute truth. The morality of the ancient Eastern

man goes back to the "divinely established" norms and rules aimed at restoring sacred traditions in actions and activities. A.Y. Gurevich says: "The movement of people towards the divine image in the sky connected them with God and became a reality in morality[7]". All people's activities (production, public, family) gain meaning by the extent to which they participate in sacred ceremonies. In traditional society, the words "ancient" and "good" are synonymous, guaranteeing ancient goodness. That is why the house and equipment, clothing and food have changed little for thousands of years. Literary genres and art genres are also stable. New ehrams not only replaced the old ones, but also restored their "original model". According to I.V. Klochkov, modern people see the world in motion and development. The concepts of "evolution" and "progress" are concepts that pave the way for creating the image of the world.

The word civilization is a Latin word that means citizenship, belonging to citizenship, belonging to the state[8]. Analyzing the concept of civilization, in the process of studying the views of the existing literature on this subject, special attention is paid to the various directions of socio-economic development of society based on the analysis of this concept, which allows us to understand the essence of the concept of civilization as a social phenomenon in general forms. In all sources, it is mentioned that the concept of civilization is derived from the Latin word, and the meaning of this word is citizenship and citizenship.

The Scottish historian and philosopher A. Fergusson (1723-1816) was one of the first to analyze the concept of civilization in the sense of a certain stage of the world historical process. French statesman and philosopher A. Turgot uses this term as a broad concept of development in his book "Friend of Women" or "Treatise on Civilization" published in 1768. In the views of the French Enlightenment, it was recommended to call a society based on reason and justice a "civilized" state or society. The distinction between the concepts of culture and civilization was put forward by Spengler. He used the concepts of culture and

civilization in the context of purely chronological concepts of civilization in the sense of the antipode of culture, i.e. in the sense of characterizing the crisis-like stage of human historical development, while the English sociologist and historian A. Toynbee defined a relatively closed society in the context of this concept. used to express progress. In fact, civilization seems to take precedence over culture in a certain sense. For example, the creation of simple stone tools by primitive people paved the way for civilization, but it was not yet a civilization. By creating tools of labor, primitive man paves the way for further socio-material development, a new way of life, civilization. Because civilization is a concept that represents any socialization process.

Conclusion. Villages, religions, ethnic groups, nations, religious groups all have a distinct culture of varying degrees of cultural diversity. There are cultural elements that distinguish European societies from Chinese and Indian societies. Therefore, Chinese, Indians, and Westerners cannot be part of any broad cultural stratum. They form separate civilizations. In a word, civilization is a cultural base formed by a large group of people.

Civilization is the highest level of cultural system characteristic of humans, which distinguishes them from other creatures. It is defined by language, history, religion, customs, institutions, and people's subjective self-definition. Humans have their own degrees of identification: for example, a Roman citizen names himself with different intensities. For example, they may call themselves Roman, Italian, Catholic, Christian, European, or Western. The civilization to which it belongs is the most suitable index by which it can be specified. Civilization is the biggest “we” within which we feel culturally situated, separate from all other subjects.

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